

Research

Research on the International Competitiveness of Thailand's Tourism Service Trade—Based on Comparative with Malaysia and Singapore in the Chinese Market Trade Services

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Abstract: This article is based on the theory of absolute advantage, comparative advantage, and competitive advantage theory of the industry's international competitiveness theory, this article uses a combination of qualitative and quantitative, empirical analysis and comparative analysis to analyze the tourism services of Singapore and Malaysia from the di-mension of inbound tourism. The status quo of trade development, and a comparative analysis of the current state of tourism services in Singapore and Singapore from the number of tourists and income in Singapore and Thailand.

Keywords: Tourism, Market Trade Service, International Competitiveness,

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Introduction

In today's global economy, the concept of trade has expanded beyond the exchange of physical goods. The international competitiveness of service sectors, particularly in the field of tourism, has become a key indicator of a country's overall competitiveness. With countries worldwide actively developing their tourism resources and promoting tourism service trade, the competition in the international tourism market has become increasingly intense. Notably, the significant growth in the number of Chinese tourists visiting Thailand in recent years has had a profound impact on Thailand's economic development, generating substantial income and fostering cultural exchanges between China and Thailand. As a result, the tourism service trade has emerged as a pivotal factor in the economic advancement of the service industries in both China and Thailand. Recognizing the significance of this sector, this article aims to conduct a comparative study on the international competitiveness of Singapore's tourism service trade, with a specific focus on analyzing the Chinese market. By examining and drawing lessons from the tourism development experiences of other countries, this article seeks to propose effective strategies that can enhance the international competitiveness of Thailand's tourism service trade.

The inclusion of Singapore as a comparative case study is particularly relevant due to its reputation as a global tourism hub and its successful track record in attracting international visitors. Through a comprehensive analysis of Singapore's

tourism service trade, valuable insights can be gained, offering a reference point for understanding the factors that contribute to its success and the lessons that can be applied to Thailand's tourism industry.

By delving into the dynamics of the Chinese market, this research aims to explore the specific needs, preferences, and behaviors of Chinese tourists. China, with its growing middle class and increasing disposable income, presents a vast potential market for international tourism. Understanding the intricacies of this market and tailoring strategies to cater to Chinese tourists' unique requirements can significantly enhance Thailand's competitiveness and attract a larger share of Chinese visitors.

Ultimately, the objective of this research is to provide evidence-based recommendations and strategies that can bolster Thailand's international competitiveness in the tourism service trade sector. By leveraging the experiences of Singapore and conducting an in-depth analysis of the Chinese market, this study aims to contribute to the existing body of knowledge on tourism service trade and offer practical insights that can drive sustainable growth and economic development in Thailand's service industry.

In summary, this article recognizes the growing importance of tourism service trade in the global economy and highlights the impact of Chinese tourists on Thailand's economic development. By conducting a comparative study on Singapore's tourism service trade and analyzing the Chinese market, this research aims to provide valuable insights and propose strategies to enhance Thailand's international competitiveness in the tourism sector.

General Development of Thailand's Tourism Service Trade

Following World War II, trade in services has experienced continuous growth alongside the economic expansion of nations. According to data from the World Bank, in 2014, the proportion of global tourism service trade to GDP was merely 3.1%. However, over time, the impact of tourism service trade on the economy has steadily increased. By 2019, the global tourism industry's contribution to the global economy had reached 10.4%, becoming a significant driving force behind economic growth. This illustrates that service trade has become a crucial aspect for evaluating a country's economic strength. Service trade, particularly tourism service trade, enhances the efficiency and quality of a nation's economy through the development of an industrial chain, thereby promoting sustainable economic growth. According to statistics from the World Tourism Organization (WTO), tourism services accounted for 23.90% of total service trade in 2019. Moreover, the added value of tourism service trade reached USD 1.44 trillion in the same year, indicating its positive contribution to economic growth. A country's overall service trade competitiveness is strengthened by the competitiveness of its tourism service trade, enhancing its position in the global economic landscape.

Main Tourist Resources

Thailand boasts a rich cultural heritage that serves as a significant tourism resource. Among these resources, Buddhist culture, customs, and natural landscapes hold particular prominence. The country's vibrant Buddhist culture is reflected in its brightly colored structures, earning Thailand the reputation of "The Kingdom of the Yellow Robe." Bangkok, the capital city, is home to around 400 Buddhist temples, with the Grand Palace and Wat Phra Kaew being the most popular among tourists. The Chakri Palace is also a frequented destination, showcasing extraordinary architectural artistry that is both unique and splendid. Thailand also hosts numerous colorful traditional cultural festivals, showcasing its distinctive colors and captivating folk customs. These festivals play a crucial role in attracting foreign tourists and supporting Thailand's tourism industry. Additionally, the country's abundant animal and plant resources, as well as its coastal areas, are renowned worldwide. With its stunning and extensive coastline, tranquil bays, and unique geographical features, Thailand's tourist attractions hold an irresistible allure for visitors.

The State of Tourism Infrastructure

Thailand boasts a well-developed transportation industry, particularly in the field of air transportation, both for international and domestic travel. The country offers an increasing number of international flight routes and affordable airfares, allowing tourists to save on travel costs. However, the road and railway infrastructure in Thailand face certain challenges due to the complex terrain, including mountains. Despite this, Thailand's railway system connects major cities to Bangkok. The Bangkok National Railway Station operates express trains to the north, northeast, and south of Thailand. International trains, long-distance trains, and weekend tourist special trains can also be inquired about and reserved. Moreover, long-distance passenger transport across various parts of Thailand is highly developed. Bangkok has three major long-distance bus terminals serving southbound, eastbound, and northbound routes. The extensive long-distance bus network enables convenient travel to cities throughout the country. When it comes to accommodation, Thailand offers a wide range of options, from luxurious five-star hotels to simple tents and huts. The prices are reasonable and affordable. As tourism plays a pivotal role in Thailand's economic development, the hotel service industry serves as a vital pillar supporting the growth of the tourism sector. Therefore, Thailand places great importance on the

operation and management of various hotel accommodations. Hotels of all sizes are renowned for their cleanliness, affordability, friendly hospitality, and world-class service.

Number of Inbound Tourists Received

Inbound tourism refers to the activities where citizens of other countries enter their destination country for tourism purposes. According to data from the World Bank database, the number of inbound tourists in Thailand has consistently increased since the 1990s. Table 3.1 and Figure 3.1 illustrate this growth trend over time. In 1995, Thailand received 6.952 million inbound tourists, while in 2017, the number reached 35.592 million, nearly five times the figure from 1995. The growth rate of inbound tourists in Thailand has generally been positive, with a particularly significant increase between 2010 and 2013, during which the number of inbound tourists experienced a continuous growth rate of over 10%. However, there were some periods during which the number of inbound tourists declined due to factors such as health crises (e.g., the SARS outbreak in East Asia in 2003), natural disasters (e.g., the Sumatra Tsunami), and the global economic crisis (e.g., the U.S. subprime mortgage crisis in 2008). Nevertheless, these fluctuations did not disrupt the overall growth trend of inbound tourism to Thailand. From a comparative perspective, as shown in Table 3.2, Thailand ranked 16th in the world in terms of the number of inbound tourists in 1995, second only to Turkey. By 2017, Thailand had moved up to the 10th position globally, ranking second only to Germany. This indicates that Thailand has been increasingly favored by international tourists compared to other countries. Additionally, Table 3.2 reveals that the economic development of countries like China, Turkey, and Thailand has led to a surge in tourism, making these rapidly growing nations more popular among residents of other countries.

Year	Number of people	Growth rate	Year	Number of people	Growth rate
1995	695.2		2007	1446.4	4.64%
1996	724.4	4.20%	2008	1458.4	0.83%
1997	729.4	0.69%	2009	1415	-2.98%
1998	784.3	7.53%	2010	1593.6	12.62%
1999	865.1	10.30%	2011	1923	20.67%
2000	957.9	10.73%	2012	2235.4	16.25%
2001	1013.3	5.78%	2013	2654.7	18.76%
2002	1087.3	7.30%	2014	2481	-6.54%
2003	1008.2	-7.27%	2015	2992.3	20.61%
2004	1173.7	16.42%	2016	3253	8.71%
2005	1156.7	-1.45%	2017	3559.2	9.41%
2006	1382.2	19.50%			

Changes in the number of inbound tourists in Thailand (unit: ten thousand people) and growth rate changes from 1995 to 2017Data source: According to the official data of world bank

Country (1995)	Number of inbound tourists (1995)	Country (2017)	Number of inbound tourists (2017)
France	6003.3	France	8686.1
USA	4331.8	Spain	8178.6
Spain	3297.1	USA	7694.1
Italy	3105.2	China	6074

UK	2171.9	Italy	5825.3
Mexico	2024.1	Mexico	3929.1
China	2003.4	UK	3765.1
Poland	1921.5	Turkey	3760.1
Austria	1717.3	Germany	3745.2
Canada	1693.2	Thailand	3559.2
Germany	1484.7	Austria	2946
Russian	1029	Japan	2869.1
Greece	1013	Hong Kong	2788.4
Malaysia	746.9	Greece	2719.4
Turkey	708.3	Malaysia	2594.8
Thailand	695.2	Russian	2439
Switzerland	694.6	Canada	2079.8
Holland	657.4	Poland	1825.8
Singapore	607	Holland	1792.4
Belgium	556	Macao	1725.5

Number of inbound tourists (unit: ten thousand people) and ranking of the top 20 countries in the world in 1995 and 2017

Data source: According to the official data of the world bank

Inbound Tourism Income

Inbound tourism income serves as a crucial indicator of a country's (or region's) tourism service trade and its foreign exchange earnings. Unlike the number of inbound tourists, the income generated from inbound tourism provides a better reflection of the destination's tourism resources and supporting facilities. As depicted in Table 3.3 and Figure 3.2, Thailand's tourism revenue witnessed significant growth from 1995 to 2017. During this period, tourism revenue escalated from an initial US\$9.257 billion to US\$62.158 billion, an almost sevenfold increase.

Examining the growth rate of tourism revenue, it is evident that, aside from certain years influenced by external factors such as the Southeast Asian financial crisis in 1997, the tsunami disaster in 2004, and the US subprime mortgage crisis in 2008, Thailand's international tourism income has generally sustained a rapid growth rate.

However, it also highlights the susceptibility of international tourism revenue to unpredictable events.

Table 3.4 illustrates the changes in tourism revenue among the top 20 countries globally in terms of international tourism income for 1995 and 2017. This perspective allows us to observe Thailand's evolving competitiveness in international tourism service trade. In 1995, Thailand ranked 12th in the world for international tourism income, but by 2017, it had climbed to the fourth position. This shift not only signifies Thailand's increasing appeal to foreign tourists but also indicates that the country has made strides in enhancing service quality and infrastructure, thereby attracting a greater number of visitors who are willing to spend on their tourism experiences.

1995-2017 Thailand's inbound tourism revenue (unit: ten thousand US dollars) change and growth rate change table

Year	Tourism income	Growth rate	Year	Tourism income	Growth rate
1995	925700	11.991%	2007	2062500	24.068%
1996	1036700	-12.684%	2008	2251000	9.139%
1997	905200	-12.130%	2009	1981100	-11.990%

1998	795400	18.381%	2010	2379600	20.115%
1999	941600	5.512%	2011	3092400	29.955%
2000	993500	-5.606%	2012	3776600	22.125%
2001	937800	10.770%	2013	4573800	21.109%
2002	1038800	0.655%	2014	4204700	-8.070%
2003	1045600	24.847%	2015	4852700	15.411%
2004	1305400	-7.285%	2016	5246500	8.115%
2005	1210300	37.354%	2017	6215800	18.475%
2006	1662400	11.991%			

Data source: According to the official data of the world bank

International tourism revenue (unit: ten thousand US dollars) and ranking of the top 20 countries in the world in 1995 and 2017

Country (1995)	International tourism income (1995)	Country (2017)	International tourism income (2017)
USA	9374300	USA	25136100
France	3129500	France	6989400
Italy	3041100	Spain	6843700
UK	2757700	Thailand	6215800
Spain	2736900	Germany	5617300
Germany	2405200	UK	5147400
Austria	1452900	Italy	4454800
Switzerland	1135400	Australia	4398200
Holland	1061100	Hong Kong	3803900
Australia	1037000	Japan	3697900
Hong Kong	960400	Macao	3572600
Thailand	925700	China	3261700
Canada	917600	Turkey	3187000
China	873000	India	2787800
Singapore	761100	Mexico	2246700
Poland	692700	Austria	2240800
Mexico	684700	Portugal	2109900
Korea	667000	United Arab Emirates	2104800

Portugal	564600	Canada	2040400
Indonesia	522900	Holland	2035200

Data source: According to the official data of world bank
Inbound Tourism as a Percentage of the Global Tourism Market

To demonstrate the competitiveness of Thailand's international tourism service trade and its changing international standing, this article examines the number of inbound tourists received by Thailand and the evolving share of inbound tourism revenue in the global tourism market. Figure 3.3 provides a visual representation of Thailand's share of the global tourism market. It is evident from the figure that both the global share of inbound tourist arrivals and the global share of inbound tourism revenue have experienced an upward trend over time. Particularly noteworthy is the significant increase in the share of inbound tourism revenue in the global market, rising from 1.91% in 1995 to 4.07% in 2017. This data clearly reflects the growing international competition of Thailand's inbound tourism sector and its position within the global tourism services market.

For Singapore Overview of the Development of Singapore's Tourism Service Trade

Singapore, an urbanized country located on the southern side of the Malay Peninsula, consists of several small islands, with the main island of Singapore being the most prominent. Known as a beautiful garden city, Singapore has developed its tourism industry into one of the most vital economic sectors. In 2016, Singapore's tourism industry achieved significant accomplishments in the global market. The number of inbound tourists reached 16.4 million, reflecting an increase of 1.2 million compared to 2015, marking a growth rate of 7.7%. In terms of tourism revenue, Singapore recorded SGD 24.8 billion (approximately RMB 122.1 billion) in 2016, indicating an SGD 3 billion (approximately RMB 14.7 billion) increase from 2015, with a growth rate of approximately 13.9%. These figures represented record highs for both the number of inbound tourists and tourism income in Singapore.

Inbound Tourist Reception

Despite its small size and limited natural and cultural attractions, Singapore has experienced rapid growth in its tourism economy. In 2016, the number of mainland Chinese tourists visiting Singapore reached 2,864,000, marking a significant increase of 36% compared to 2015. Specifically, the number of Chinese tourists visiting Singapore increased by 11% year-on-year, reaching 737,000. This growth can be attributed to the opening of direct flights between Singapore and Chinese second-tier cities such as Chongqing, Zhengzhou, and Dalian. The expansion into second-tier markets has revealed substantial potential, with 802,000 tourists from 16 second-tier markets visiting Singapore in 2016, representing a remarkable 53% increase from the previous year. Currently, there are 32 cities in Mainland China with direct flights to Singapore, totaling 349 flights per week, greatly facilitating travel for tourists.

Changes in the number of inbound tourists from Singapore from 1995 to 2017

Data source: World Bank official website

Inbound Tourism Income

From 1995 to 2017, Singapore's annual inbound tourism revenue amounted to US\$9,225 million, which accounted for approximately 1.3% of the global tourism revenue. In 2009, the inbound tourism revenue was affected by the economic crisis, resulting in a decrease of 0.03 percentage points compared to the previous year. However, in 2010, the revenue rebounded to US\$14,178 million, representing a significant increase of 53.7% compared to 2009. In general, with the

exception of the downturn in 2009, Singapore's inbound tourism revenue has been steadily increasing over the years. As shown in Figure 3-5:

Data source: World Bank official website

Inbound Tourism as a Percentage of the Global Tourism Market

As shown in Figure 3-6, Singapore's share of the global tourism market in terms of inbound tourists was approximately 0.8% from 1995 to 2017. Over this period, the global number of inbound tourists displayed a fluctuating trend. Singapore's inbound tourism revenue accounted for around 1.3% of the global tourism revenue and also exhibited a fluctuating pattern. In recent years, there has been an increase in both the number of inbound tourists and the proportion of inbound tourism revenue in the global market. This indicates a shift in the focus of the world's tourism market towards emerging tourism destinations

The number of inbound tourists received by Singapore and the share of inbound tourism revenue in the international tourism market from 1995 to 2017

Data source: World Bank official website

For Malaysia

Overview of the Development of Malaysia's Tourism Service Trade

Malaysia, located in the heart of Southeast Asia, is a tropical island country situated near the equator. It benefits from a pleasant climate and a strategic geographical location, which provides Malaysia with distinctive natural tourism resources. As a result, Malaysia has been recognized as one of the most desirable tourist destinations by the World Economic Forum. The tourism service trade plays a significant role in Malaysia's economy, generating substantial income and ranking as the country's third-largest source of foreign exchange earnings.

Inbound Tourist Reception

Malaysia has experienced rapid growth in inbound tourism. Although its tourism industry developed later compared to Singapore and Thailand, it has surpassed them in terms of the number of inbound tourists over the past two decades, establishing itself as the largest tourist destination in Southeast Asia. While there was a sharp decline in inbound tourist numbers in 2003 due to the SARS epidemic and the Iraq war, Malaysia consistently maintained a positive growth rate in the remaining years. Even during the global economic crisis in 2008 and 2009, Malaysia's inbound tourism continued to grow significantly. In 2014, the country reached a record high of 27.43 million inbound tourists.

Changes in the number of inbound tourists from Singapore from 1995 to 2017

Data source: World Bank official website

Inbound Tourism Income

According to the data, Malaysia has experienced rapid growth in inbound tourism income, showcasing the increasing economic benefits of the tourism sector. It ranks as the second largest earner of tourism revenue in Southeast Asia. From 1995 to 2017, Malaysia's average annual income from inbound tourism was approximately US\$100 million, contributing to a share of the global tourism revenue. In particular, the income from inbound tourism witnessed a significant increase of nearly 35.5% in 2007 compared to 2006, reflecting the successful outcomes of the "2007 Malaysia Tourism Year" activities. However, in 2009, the economic crisis resulted in a decline in inbound tourism income, while other years experienced varying degrees of growth in foreign exchange from tourism. It is worth noting that since 2014, due to the Malaysia Airlines crash, tourism revenue started to decline, highlighting the sensitivity of the Malaysian inbound tourism market to external factors and its vulnerability. Figure 3-8 illustrates the income from Malaysia's inbound tourism and its changes from 1995 to 2017.

Changes in Malaysia's inbound tourism revenue from 1995 to 2017

Data source: World Bank official website

Inbound Tourism as a Percentage of the Global Tourism Market

From 1995 to 2017, the number of inbound tourists received by Malaysia accounted for approximately 1.5% of the total global reception, indicating its position in the global tourism market. Similarly, the income from inbound tourism in Malaysia accounted for approximately 2.1% of the global tourism revenue. Both indicators demonstrate the international status of Malaysia's inbound tourism sector. The number of inbound tourists and the income from inbound tourism displayed similar trends over this period. The tourism industry experienced a downturn in 2003 due to the SARS

outbreak, but gradually recovered. However, there was a significant decline in 2014 following the Malaysia Airlines incident, which had a notable impact on the development of tourism in Malaysia.

The number of inbound tourists received by Singapore and the share of inbound tourism revenue in the international tourism market from 1995 to 2017

Data source: World Bank official website

Comparison of the Development Status of Tourism Service Trade in Singapore, Malaysia and Thailand

The development status of tourism service trade in Singapore, Malaysia, and Thailand can be compared based on the number of tourists received in the inbound tourism market and the inbound tourism revenue.

In terms of the number of inbound tourists, Malaysia receives the highest number among the three countries. It has consistently attracted a large number of tourists, making it the largest tourist destination in Southeast Asia. Thailand follows closely behind Malaysia in terms of the number of inbound tourists, while Singapore receives a comparatively smaller number.

In terms of inbound tourism revenue, Thailand surpasses both Malaysia and Singapore. Thailand's tourism industry generates significant income from inbound tourists, indicating its strong position in the global tourism market. Malaysia's inbound tourism revenue is also notable, though slightly lower than Thailand. Singapore, on the other hand, has a lower level of inbound tourism revenue compared to both Malaysia and Thailand.

When comparing the overall tourism service trade of the three countries, Malaysia stands out with its high number of inbound tourists. Thailand excels in terms of inbound tourism revenue, while Singapore lags behind in both categories. Additionally, a comprehensive analysis can be done by comparing the structure and competitiveness of tourism in Singapore, Malaysia, and Thailand. This analysis would consider factors such as tourism resources, infrastructure, marketing strategies, and overall attractiveness to tourists. Such a comparison would provide a more detailed understanding of the tourism service trade in these countries.

Comparison of Total

When comparing the total tourism service trade of Singapore, Malaysia, and Thailand, it can be observed that Malaysia and Thailand have relatively close levels of development in the tourism industry. Both countries possess abundant tourism resources and have well-established tourism sectors. In 2015, Thailand's total tourism trade amounted to approximately \$60 billion, while Singapore's total tourism trade reached \$46.3 billion.

Despite Malaysia starting its tourism trade relatively later, it has experienced rapid growth and its development has not been significantly hindered. The tourism sector in Malaysia plays a crucial role in driving overall economic development.

Singapore, being the only developed country among the three, has a relatively modest endowment of tourism resources. However, its strong domestic economy and high living standards have contributed to the successful development of its tourism service trade.

Overall, while Malaysia and Thailand demonstrate robust growth and possess substantial tourism resources, Singapore has managed to excel in tourism service trade due to its strong domestic economy and high standards of living.

Comparison of tourism competitiveness structure

When comparing the tourism competitiveness structure of Singapore, Malaysia, and Thailand, we can refer to the World Economic Forum's tourism competitiveness index. This index comprises three main categories, 13 sub-indicators, and 58 individual indicators. It assesses 139 countries and regions based on factors such as regulatory structure, business

environment, infrastructure, human resources, cultural resources, and natural resources. These indicators encompass both hard data obtained from international, national, or regional institutions and non-governmental organisations, as well as soft data derived from questionnaire surveys completed by senior managers.

In the 2017 Global Tourism Competitiveness World Rankings, Singapore, Malaysia, and Thailand were ranked 13th, 26th, and 34th, respectively. Singapore significantly outperformed the other two countries and was positioned among the world's developed countries in terms of tourism competitiveness.

This ranking reflects Singapore's strong position in the global tourism market and its advanced regulatory framework, well-developed infrastructure, skilled workforce, rich cultural resources, and attractive natural attractions. Malaysia and Thailand also demonstrated competitive tourism sectors, although their rankings were comparatively lower. The rankings suggest areas where Malaysia and Thailand could further enhance their tourism competitiveness to improve their overall position in the global tourism market.

World Ranking of Singapore-Malaysia Tourism Competitiveness

Indicator name	Singapore	Malaysia	Thailand
Tourism Competitiveness Index	13	26	34
Environmental regulations	2	17	45
law and order	6	41	118
Health and hygiene	62	77	90
Travel priority	2	55	34
Enterprise environment and infrastructure	2	17	45
Aviation facilities	6	21	20
Land transportation facilities	2	34	72
Tourist facility	24	46	16
Communication information facilities	14	39	58
Tourism price competitiveness	91	3	18
Human Resources	5	22	40
National tourism image	1	35	52
Natural resources	24	46	16
Cultural resources	28	34	37

Source: Compiled based on data from the 2017 Tourism Competitiveness Report of the World Economic Forum

Conclusion

In conclusion, the tourism service trade in Thailand, Singapore, and Malaysia has experienced significant development in recent years. As emerging tourist destinations, these countries have been able to attract a large number of international tourists and generate substantial income from inbound tourism.

Thailand stands out with the highest number of Chinese tourists and the highest income from inbound tourism among the three countries. This indicates that Thailand has successfully positioned itself as a popular destination for Chinese tourists and has effectively capitalised on the economic benefits of inbound tourism.

On the other hand, Malaysia has achieved a consistently high average annual number of inbound tourists, surpassing both Thailand and Singapore in this aspect. This demonstrates Malaysia's ability to attract and accommodate a significant number of international visitors, contributing to its tourism industry's growth and overall economic development.

Singapore, despite having a relatively mediocre resource endowment, has managed to leverage its strong domestic economic strength to develop a well-performing tourism service trade. It ranks lower than Thailand and Malaysia in terms of inbound tourist reception and tourism revenue but still maintains a competitive position in the global tourism market.

Overall, these three countries showcase the potential and importance of tourism service trade as a driving force for economic growth. The competition for international tourism resources has become intense, prompting these destinations to continuously enhance their tourism offerings and competitiveness to attract more visitors and reap the benefits of a thriving tourism industry.

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